

Hooking the Network with Bettercap and BeEF-XSS

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Abstract- BeEF is a penetration testing tool that works on web browser exploitation. BeEF explores exploitability in the context of the one open door: the web browser, looking beyond the fortified network perimeter and client system. From within the browser context, BeEF will hook one or more web browsers and utilise them as beachheads for launching directed command modules and other assaults on the system. Bettercap, a man-in-the-middle attack tool developed for users who are likely to be penetration testers to check and improve the safety of networks or some devices connected to these networks. This paper explains practical demonstration how we can hook a network with BEeF and Bettercap.

Keywords- BeEF(Browser Exploitation Framework), cross-site scripting, Bettercap, network, exploit.

I. INTRODUCTION

BEeF-XSS is a program that's going to help us understand browser exploitation using cross-site scripting and this paper proposes a method how to use it with bettercap efficiently. We are going to inject scripts of beef hook and hook-up the victim with bettercap. As we know the bettercap is a tool developed for penetration testing to test and improve the security of networks or some devices connected to these networks.

Bettercap could be a capable, effectively extensible and versatile system composed. It aims to provide security researchers, red teamers, and engineers with an easy-to-use, all-in-one solution with all of the features they might possibly require for monitoring and assaulting Wi-Fi systems, Bluetooth Low Energy devices, wireless HID devices, and IPv4/IPv6 networks. Using both the tools to hook a whole network make it gain control over the browser. And also we can execute the BeEF modules in real sites so that user doesn't know that he is exploited.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

¹Brigitte Lundeen, ²Dr. Jim Alves-Foss has done a study on clickjacking [4] which is one of the vulnerability that can be used to exploit the browser. Clickjacking is to trick the user to click on something that's actually not what the user perceives they are clicking on. The clickjacking is performed using a penetration testing tool called BeEF. This tool is designed to for professional penetration testers to demonstrate the client-side security vulnerabilities. In the paper, they present a plugin module for BeEF which

shows the impact of clickjacking vulnerabilities to the penetration testers.

In BeEF, clickjacking is a very specific type of attack. All BeEF modules adhere to a precise set of guidelines and are subject to certain method limitations. Clickjacking works as a module, but because of the nature of the attack, having it as a separate page within BeEF may allow for additional extensibility. There are more benefits using BeEF for clickjacking. Ability to perform chain attacks is one of the features. An attacker can use an XSS module to plan an attack and then utilise BeEF's clickjacking module to execute it.

III. EXISTING TOOL

A. BeEF

The Browser Exploitation Framework is a tool for performing web browser penetration testing. It has developed to incorporate practical implementations of any client-side attack vectors. It exhibits cross-site scripting problems in the browser. BeEF is a popular online security solution that is free and open-source. Because the underlying framework is versatile, including my code as a module makes many of BeEF's pre-existing capabilities available, reducing development time. It will be easier to chain assaults if you have a stable structure with a variety of modules. To carry out an advanced attack, for example, you'll employ cross-site scripting and bettercap.

B. Starting BeEF

To start BeEF enter the command `sudo beef-xss` and press enter & type in your password. Using the link that appears we can open the BeEF control panel, you have to enter the username and password in order to access the control panel.

When a browser is hooked the below shown window appears, using those commands we can perform penetration testing.

Then enter **help http.proxy**, we will get some information regarding how to setup the http.proxy.

IV. USING BEEF WITH BETTERCAP

A. Working BeEF with Bettercap

By using BeEF with the Bettercap we can gain more control over than we just use BeEF. Now we are going to use the BeEF to hook the whole network. So, that when get access any site with http protocol and hook the browser. And we can perform the various exploitation commands in BeEF.

Then enter the command, **sudo bettercap -iface eth0**

Now we want to turn on a subscribe using the command **set http.proxy.sslstrip true**

Now we want to navigate to a http website.

Then enter command **net.probe on**, it turns on the net.probe.

And now we enter a command **set http.proxy.injectjs** and add the url path or javascript code to inject into every html page.

And then we have turn on the **net.sniff** and **net.recon**.

Copying the ip that is in the hook

These pictures are example for the browser exploitation framework used with bettercap. Two sites with http protocol is accessed and hooked. The clippy and pretty theft vulnerability testing are performed.

B. Limitations

It does not work on the webpages with https protocol and the browser exploitation cannot be performed. As we know HTTP is a set of rules and standards that regulate how information can be sent across the Internet. HTTP establishes communication standards for web browsers and servers. HTTP is a network protocol that runs on top of TCP at the application layer. Hypertext structured text is used by HTTP to provide a logical relationship between text nodes. It's also known as the "stateless protocol," because each command is run independently, without reference to the previous run command.

HTTPS is a secure and enhanced version of HTTP. For data communication, it uses port 443. By encrypting all communication using SSL, it provides for secure transactions. It's a hybrid of the SSL/TLS and HTTP

protocols. It allows a network server to be identified in an encrypted and safe manner. HTTP also enables the server and browser to establish a secure encrypted connection. It provides data security in both directions. This assists you in preventing the theft of potentially sensitive information.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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